

THE EXPERIENCE OF DEVELOPED COUNTRIES IN TAXING OF INDIVIDUALS

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Abstract: The article examines the issues of taxation of individuals based on the experience of developed countries. Information is also provided on property tax levied on individuals.

Keywords: Tax, real estate, local tax, Property tax of individuals

Introduction

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the income of individuals is taxed in accordance with the "Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan". In accordance with the "Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan", an individual who permanently resides in the Republic of Uzbekistan during the fiscal year or who has lived in Uzbekistan for 183 days or more during any period up to 12 months starting with the fiscal year 0 of the Republic of Uzbekistan is considered a resident. Individuals who are residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan are taxed on their income from sources of activity in the Republic of Uzbekistan as well as outside it. Amounts of personal income tax paid outside the Republic of Uzbekistan are taken into account when paying taxes in the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The amount of the amount to be taken into account should not exceed the amount of income tax of individuals calculated according to the rates applicable in the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to the tax legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, tax payers are divided into legal entities and individuals. Taxes paid by individuals make up 20-25% of state budget revenues. The nature of taxes paid by individuals is that the tax is collected directly from the individual's

own income. The taxes and fees they pay are mainly transferred to the budget in cash.

Many economists have conducted scientific-theoretical studies on taxing individuals and collecting taxes from them. In particular, in the opinion of Professor O. Adurahmanov, taxes from individuals are equivalent compulsory payments that citizens transfer to the state from their personal incomes based on the sources of any legal activity.

Uzbek scientist A. Adizov stated that "Taxes collected from individuals are fees for services provided by the state and society as an obligation, and the amount and amount determined by law in order to provide them with funds are payments that are compulsorily levied at the discretion of the state in the established terms". The author of this definition, like some foreign economists, is not limited to emphasizing the responsibility of the population in terms of taxes, but also emphasizes that the state must fulfill its obligations in a fair manner, and the funds collected through these mandatory taxes are the public's emphasizes the need to spend sparingly based on their interests and provide detailed information to payers in this regard. Based on these scientific approaches, the taxes paid by individuals are primarily directed to improving their capabilities and protecting their interests, - it is possible to summarize the opinions.

Individuals pay the following taxes and other mandatory payments to the state budget:

- tax on the income of individuals;
- property tax;
- land tax;
- tax for the use of gasoline, diesel fuel and gas for vehicles;
- a fixed rate tax imposed on the income of individuals engaged in business activities;
- other taxes and mandatory payments stipulated by law.

In all developed foreign countries, the tax imposed on the property of individuals is of particular importance. It should be noted that this tax in the tax system of these countries has many common features and at the same time differs from each other. Property taxes occupy a small place in the total amount of state taxes and are included in the category of local taxes in most countries.

Methods and results

In developed countries, property taxation is carried out in two ways. 1. Tax on the total amount of property 2. Taxes on separate types of property.

Tax on the total amount of property, in turn, is divided into tax on personal property of natural persons and property tax of legal entities. The value of the property of individuals is deducted from the personal property tax. The value of the property is estimated based on the market or cadastral value determined by the methods developed according to the current laws. Personal property tax can be levied at a single rate or on the basis of a differentiated progressive rate of taxation. A single rate of taxation applies in Germany, Belgium, Iceland and Luxembourg. A progressive system of taxation applies in Sweden, Finland, Norway, Spain, Switzerland and other countries.

An important feature of the personal property tax is the sufficiently high initial amount to be taxed. In addition, in many cases significant benefits are provided for different groups of taxpayers. Personal property tax rarely exceeds 0.5 percent of total tax revenue. All property taxes apply to regional or local taxes, but the levy threshold is often set at the central level. Special property taxes are historically preserved taxes. The share of these taxes in total tax revenue varies greatly among developed countries. If in Great Britain this share is more than 10 percent, in Belgium, Greece, Austria, Italy, Luxembourg, Turkey, Finland, Switzerland, Sweden, and Spain they are more than 1 percent. Countries with high incomes in terms of taxes on certain types of property are the USA (over 9 percent), Canada (over 8 percent), New Zealand (around 6 percent), Australia (almost 5 percent), Ireland (2.5 percent), France (2 around percent).

In the US, property taxes are paid by individuals. Property taxes are levied in most states. Tax rates vary by state. The employees of the tax office, who are engaged in the assessment of real estate, are called tax assessors. Property tax revenues make up about 9.0 percent of all levels of government tax revenues. In the US, property taxes are levied at the state and municipal level. This tax mainly applies to real estate and farm equipment, with the exception of property owned by non-profit organizations and not used by them for commercial purposes. Also, assets of the federal government, state governments, and local governments are exempt from taxation. In 13 states, intangible assets: stocks, debt obligations, etc. are taxed. Personal real estate and means of production belonging to citizens are also taxed. At the state level, the following tax rates are set: 0.75 percent of the corporation's capital and 0.5 percent to 5.0 percent for the taxable property of legal entities and individuals. In addition, a tax is levied at the municipal level. A portion of the property tax is included in US state taxes. Although it exists in a number of states, their weight in the source of income is not large, i.e. less than 3 percent. Property taxes play no role in the federal budget. As part of local taxes, they make up 3/4 of the income. This is equal to 12% of the total tax revenue.

In Great Britain, the tax on real estate of individuals is one of the main taxes that form the local budget. Rent payment is the tax base. It is collected from real estate owners or tenants. Therefore, they are property tax payers and are property owners or participants. Real estate means land. Also, these taxpayers include those who rent housing and those who pay the rent for an apartment.

Real estate value is usually assessed once every 10 years. Real estate value reflects the annual income from renting out a particular property. Since the property tax forms the local budget, the tax rate is determined by the local government. Of course, it is determined based on the demand for financial resources of the local authorities. Because of this, property tax in the UK varies significantly between different cities and counties.

Property tax in Germany has a long history. This tax was introduced by King Rudolph von Habsburg in 1278. From January 1, 1955, the tax rate on the total property of an individual was increased to 1%. Until then, the tax rate was 0.5 percent. A tax rate of 0.6 percent has been set for industrial enterprises and companies. Agricultural and forestry property has benefits in the form of a reduced tax amount.

In the Japanese tax system, property tax has a special place and forms one of the three major groups of taxes, mainly, property tax group. Unlike in our country, legal entities and individuals pay this tax at the same rate in Japan. Usually this is 1.4% of the property value. Revaluation of property is carried out once in 3 years. The taxable object includes all real estate, land, securities, interest on bank deposits. The tax is also paid when the property is transferred from one owner to another, that is, at the time of sale or purchase of property.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one of the distinguishing factors of the tax system of Uzbekistan from the international tax practice is the lack of a mechanism for taxation based on the general declaration of income, and it has been criticized that the mechanism of taxing existing incomes based on declaration in Uzbekistan is not comprehensive. Also, according to the results of the analysis, there is a high potential for increasing the share of personal income tax in the state budget in Uzbekistan, and for this, it is necessary to increase the number of taxpayers and expand the tax base. and it was scientifically concluded that the mechanism of taxing income based on the declaration is considered the most effective instrument.

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